

Structural analysis on molten rare-earth fluorides^ψ

Sou Watanabe^a, Ashok K. Adya^b, Yoshihiro Okamoto^c, Hiroshi Akatsuka^a and Haruaki Matsuura^a

^aResearch Laboratory for Nuclear Reactors, Tokyo Institute of Technology, 2-12-1-N1-10, Ookayama, Meguro-ku, Tokyo 152-8550, Japan

^bCondensed Matter Group, School of Contemporary Sciences, University of Abertay Dundee, Bell Street, Dundee, DD1 1HG, UK

^cNuclear Science and Energy Directorate, Japan Atomic Energy Agency, Tokai-mura, Naka-gun, Ibaraki, 319-1195, Japan

E-mail : souwata@nr.titech.ac.jp

Fax : 81-3-5734-3057

Manuscript received 6 June 2005

Local structures of molten rare earth fluorides LnF₃ (Ln = Gd, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, Lu) around lanthanide ions are investigated by extended X-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy. Inter-ionic distances and coordination numbers of first neighbouring fluoride ions around lanthanide ions are evaluated by curve-fitting analysis on the predominant peak in the 1st coordination shell of each lanthanide fluoride. Coordination numbers do not depend on the type of rare earth element, and they fall in the range 6-7, while the inter-ionic distances change proportionately with the ionic radius of the rare earth.

Local structures of molten lanthanide trichlorides have been widely investigated¹ by both experiments and numerical calculations so far. This is particularly important because the available structural data along with other relevant information on thermodynamic, electrochemical, physico-chemical properties, etc. can be used for nuclear engineering applications based on pyrochemistry². Also, since the physico-chemical properties of molten salts are strongly correlated to the local structures that exist in the melts, formulation of reliable structural database is important for developing new industrial applications using molten salts based technologies. However, the structural information available on molten fluorides is relatively scanty. This is mainly due to the difficulty in handling these materials at high temperatures, and finding suitable containers to overcome the associated corrosion problems. We have already successfully evaluated the structures of some molten fluorides using X-ray absorption fine structure (XAFS) technique³. Following the similar procedures, local structures of molten lanthanide fluorides are also expected to be revealed by this technique.

Crystal structures of lanthanide trifluorides, LnF₃, have already been well identified⁴. LaF₃, CeF₃, PrF₃ and NdF₃ take trigonal tysonite structure in the solid state, and they

show fast ion conduction behaviour at high temperatures below their melting points. In contrast, other lanthanide trifluorides, except those mentioned previously, take orthorhombic structure at around room temperature. While SmF₃, EuF₃ and GdF₃ become tysonite type, and transit to fast ion conduction phase at higher temperature, ErF₃, TmF₃, YbF₃ and LuF₃ become trigonal directly. These structural differences in the crystalline phases of lanthanide trifluorides are considered to be caused by the differences in ionic potentials around Ln³⁺. It becomes imperative to explore the structural differences in their liquid states, and to achieve this it is necessary first to investigate systematically their local structures.

In this study, we chose orthorhombic LnF₃ (Ln = Gd, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, Lu) salts, and investigated their local structures in the liquid states by XAFS measurements. Systematic structural data of these molten fluorides would contribute towards gaining fundamental information necessary to develop pyrochemical reprocessing system by using molten fluorides.

Experimental

Lanthanide trifluorides, LnF₃ (Ln = Gd, Dy, Ho, Er, Yb, Lu, Soekawa Co. 4N), were mixed with boron ni-

^ψDedicated to Professor H. C. Gaur on his 80th birthday.

Table 1. Experimental conditions of transmission XAFS measurements

Sample	Melting point (K)	Absorption edge, (keV)	Beamline	Monochromator	Measured temperatures (K)
GdF ₃	1504	7.243	BL7C	Si (1 1 1) double crystal	300, 1523
DyF ₃	1427	7.79	BL7C	Si (1 1 1) double crystal	300, 1473
HoF ₃	1416	8.071	BL27B	Si (1 1 1) double crystal	300, 1473
ErF ₃	1419	8.358	BL10B	Si (3 1 1) channel-cut	300, 1473
YbF ₃	1480	8.944	BL10B	Si (3 1 1) channel-cut	300, 1523
LuF ₃	1455	9.244	BL27B	Si (1 1 1) double crystal	300, 1473

tride (BN) matrix powder homogeneously, and the mixtures were pressed into pellets of 13 mm diameter and 1 mm thickness, each. Mixing weight ratio of LnF₃ and BN was about 1 : 9, and this gave appropriate X-ray absorption at the Ln-L_{III} X-ray absorption energies for XAFS analysis. Above the melting point of LnF₃ (see Table 1), BN matrix could properly hold the droplets of molten LnF₃ and keep them suspended.

Stepped scan transmission XAFS measurements were carried out at the Photon Factory of High Energy Accelerator Research Organization, Japan. Experimental conditions are listed in Table 1. The sample pellet was installed in an electric furnace located between the ionization chambers, and the sample temperature was controlled by the furnace within ± 5 K of the set value. In order to take into account the statistical fluctuations in the data, an average of five consistent scans was used for the final data analysis.

X-Ray absorption spectra were analyzed by using WinXAS 2.3 software⁵. XAFS oscillation signal, $\chi(k)$ (eq. (1)) as a function of k (the wave number of photoelectron) was extracted from the background corrected X-ray absorption spectrum by assuming that the X-ray absorption of isolated absorber is expressed as a combination of three 2nd degree polynomials.

$$\chi(k) = S_0^2 \frac{N_{\text{LnF}} F(k)}{k R_{\text{LnF}}^2} \exp(-2\sigma^2 k^2 + \frac{2}{3} C_4 k^4) \sin(2kR_{\text{LnF}} + \delta(k) - \frac{4}{3} C_3 k^3) \quad (1)$$

where, S_0^2 is the reduction factor correlated to the probability of single electron excitation; R_{LnF} , the inter-ionic

distance; N_{LnF} , the coordination number; σ^2 , the Debye-Waller factor; and C_3 and C_4 , the 3rd and 4th cumulant coefficients, respectively, and they are all fitting parameters. $F(k)$ and $\delta(k)$ are the backscattering amplitude and the phase shift, respectively, and they are theoretically calculated by FEFF 8.0 XAFS simulation code⁶. Radial structure function (RSF), $\text{FT}|\chi(k) \cdot k^3|$, was obtained by Fourier transformation of k^3 weighted XAFS oscillation, $\chi(k) \cdot k^3$ with 4th degree Bessel window function. Local structural parameters around each rare earth ion were evaluated by curve fitting analysis of eq. (1) to the first neighbouring Ln³⁺-F⁻ correlation peak in $\text{FT}|\chi(k) \cdot k^3|$.

Results and discussion

The extracted XAFS oscillations $\chi(k) \cdot k^3$ are shown in Fig. 1, where solid lines and circles show solid and liquid states, respectively. For all the samples, one can notice slight phase shifts in the XAFS oscillation upon heating, which is the typical tendency observed in molten samples³. Since any irregular or distinct oscillation can not be observed in these spectra in both the solid and liquid phases, multiple electron excitation effects can be neglected in these molten fluoride cases. This is so because, multiple electron excitation effects, which are reported to be observed at the Ln-L edge⁷, if present, should result in a ghost peak appearance in $\text{FT}|\chi(k) \cdot k^3|$ or a drastic decrease of S_0^2 .

Fourier transformed radial structure functions (RSFs), $\text{FT}|\chi(k) \cdot k^3|$, are shown in Fig. 2. Predominant peaks at ca. 2.0 Å are attributed to the Ln³⁺-F⁻ correlation. The RSFs also exhibit typical changes on melting, i.e. the peak intensities drastically decrease and the peak positions shift to shorter distances. The curve fitting analyses

Fig. 1. XAFS oscillations, $\chi(k) \cdot k^3$ of LnF_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}, \text{Lu}$) in solid (lines) and liquid (circles) states.

to obtain structural parameters are carried out by using these $\text{Ln}^{3+}-\text{F}^-$ correlation peaks.

Local structural parameters of the nearest-neighbour $\text{Ln}^{3+}-\text{F}^-$ correlation are listed in Table 2, where S_0^2 values in the liquid phase are derived by fixing the fluorine coordination number to be 9 (@ 300 K) corresponding to orthorhombic LnF_3 crystals⁴. In addition, C_3 and C_4 , which are the correction terms related to anharmonic oscillation effects at high temperature, are fixed to be 0 at 300 K. Fitting analyses are successfully finalized with only small residuals left behind. Analytical errors of the fitted parameters are estimated by several repetition analyses of the data.

Coordination numbers of all the investigated LnF_3 molten samples are plotted as a function of Ln^{3+} in Fig. 3, and they fall in the range 6–7, and this finding is

Fig. 2. Radial structure functions (RSFs), $\text{FT}|\chi(k) \cdot k^3|$ of LnF_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}, \text{Lu}$), in solid (lines) and liquid (circles) states.

discussed below in terms of the local structure dependence in the liquid phase. Various structural investigations of rare earth halides by Raman spectroscopy⁸, XAFS⁹, diffraction measurements¹⁰, and molecular dynamics simulations¹¹ conclude that relatively heavier rare earth ($Z > 66$) trihalides, which take AlCl_3 (chlorides) or FeCl_3 (bromides) like structure in the solid state, form 6-coordinated octahedra in melts, while LnX_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}, \text{Nd}; \text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$), which take UCl_3 -like structure in the solid state are suggested to be in somewhat higher coordination than 6 in the liquid phase. Similar to the

Table 2. Structural parameters of the first-neighbouring $\text{Ln}^{3+}-\text{F}^-$ correlation obtained by curve fitting analysis

Sample	T (K)	S_0^2	N_{LnF}	R_{LnF} (Å)	σ^2 (10^{-2}Å^2)	C_3 (10^{-3}Å^3)	C_4 (10^{-4}Å^4)	Residual (%)
GdF ₃	300	0.98	9 (fix)	2.34 ± 0.00	0.77 ± 0.06	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.36
	1523	0.98 (fix)	6.39 ± 0.16	2.28 ± 0.02	3.31 ± 0.33	0.90 ± 0.18	2.71 ± 0.29	2.56
DyF ₃	300	0.89	9 (fix)	2.31 ± 0.00	0.68 ± 0.02	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.51
	1473	0.89 (fix)	6.22 ± 0.23	2.24 ± 0.01	2.74 ± 0.18	0.27 ± 0.04	2.30 ± 0.12	1.67
HoF ₃	300	0.81	9 (fix)	2.29 ± 0.00	0.63 ± 0.03	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.69
	1473	0.81 (fix)	6.42 ± 0.40	2.23 ± 0.01	2.77 ± 0.26	0.53 ± 0.07	2.50 ± 0.19	2.00
ErF ₃	300	0.80	9 (fix)	2.28 ± 0.01	0.62 ± 0.01	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.28
	1473	0.80 (fix)	6.69 ± 0.25	2.21 ± 0.01	2.69 ± 0.19	0.39 ± 0.03	1.84 ± 0.46	2.64
YbF ₃	300	0.98	9 (fix)	2.25 ± 0.00	0.66 ± 0.04	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.28
	1523	0.98 (fix)	6.74 ± 0.36	2.20 ± 0.01	2.85 ± 0.15	0.22 ± 0.06	2.33 ± 0.72	1.25
LuF ₃	300	0.95	9 (fix)	2.23 ± 0.01	0.72 ± 0.05	0 (fix)	0 (fix)	1.93
	1473	0.95 (fix)	7.14 ± 0.41	2.19 ± 0.01	2.89 ± 0.11	0.38 ± 0.14	1.82 ± 0.91	4.73

Fig. 3. Coordination numbers of molten LnF_3 versus Ln^{3+} ions, where circles, squares and triangles correspond to phase transitions in the solid phase.

suggestions on chloride and bromide melts, structures of molten fluorides are also expected to vary depending on their crystal structures.

Therefore, coordination numbers of LaF_3 , CeF_3 and NdF_3 pure melts are suspected to be higher than those obtained for LnF_3 melts investigated in this paper. These discussions are supported by our previous report¹² of XAFS analysis on molten 0.2 LnF_3 - 0.8 MF ($\text{Ln} = \text{La}, \text{Ce}, \text{Nd}, \text{Sm}; \text{M} = \text{Li}, \text{Na}, \text{K}$) systems at 1173 K. It was concluded there that the structure of those salts mainly depend on their crystal structures rather than the alkali ion species at the investigated composition, and coordination numbers of La, Ce and Nd systems were evaluated to be higher than those of Sm systems. However, structural differences between the three groups (Gd, Dy + Ho and Er + Yb + Lu) can not be unambiguously confirmed by the present XAFS measurements, although coordination numbers of the group (Er, Yb and Lu) show slightly higher values (see Fig. 3) than the other systems. This implies that some higher coordinated units other than 6-coordinated octahedra can also exist in these three melts belonging to the third group.

Ionic radii¹³ of Ln^{3+} ions, $\sigma_{\text{Ln}^{3+}}$, in 6-coordinated structures, and of fluoride ion, σ_{F^-} , are 1.078, 1.052, 1.041, 1.030, 1.008, 1.001 and 1.19 Å for Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} , Ho^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Yb^{3+} , Lu^{3+} and F^- ions, respectively. The nearest-neighbour Ln^{3+} - F^- distances, determined from the present XAFS analyses, have values almost similar to the sum of the ionic radii, $\sigma_{\text{Ln}^{3+}} + \sigma_{\text{F}^-}$, as shown in Fig. 4. This observation also suggests that all the six Ln^{3+} fluoride systems investigated here form on average the 6-coordinated octahedra in the first coordination shells as has also been observed in chloride or bromide melts.

Fig. 4. The nearest-neighbour Ln^{3+} - F^- distances of molten LnF_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{Gd}, \text{Dy}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}, \text{Lu}$) systems obtained experimentally from XAFS analysis, and the sums of ionic radii, $\sigma_{\text{Ln}^{3+}} + \sigma_{\text{F}^-}$, versus Ln^{3+} ions.

Conclusions :

Ln L_{III} -edge XAFS analysis of six molten LnF_3 (GdF_3 , DyF_3 , HoF_3 , ErF_3 , YbF_3 , LuF_3) systems revealed that, on average, 6-coordinated octahedra are formed in their 1st coordination shells. The structural parameters, such as the nearest-neighbour coordination numbers and inter-ionic distances of fluoride ions around lanthanide ions were obtained. The results are in accord with the crystal structure dependence of molten salt structure as suggested earlier for molten rare earth chlorides and bromides. Nevertheless, local structural analysis of XAFS data on LaF_3 , CeF_3 , and NdF_3 pure melts need to be carried out in the future to complete the systematic investigation of molten lanthanide fluorides.

Acknowledgements

We wish to thank Dr. M. Matsuzaki at the Tokyo Tech. for the technical assistance. These experiments have been carried out with the approval of the Photon Factory Program Advisory Committee (Proposal Nos. 2004G064, 2004G303), and cooperative research program between Tokyo Tech. and JAERI. We are also grateful to the JSPS for the financial support for the Joint Project between the Japan and UK partners under the "Japan-UK Research Cooperative Program", 99GC0006. One of us (A.K.A.) would like to thank the University of Abertay Dundee for the continued support of his research activities.

References

1. e.g. A. K. Adya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 1197.
2. e.g. Y. Okamoto, H. Hayashi and T. Ogawa, *J. Nucl. Mater.*, 1997, **247**, 86.

Watanabe *et al.* : Structural analysis on molten rare-earth fluorides

3. S. Watanabe, R. Toyoyoshi, T. Sakamoto, Y. Okamoto, Y. Iwadate, H. Akatsuka and H. Matsuura, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids*, 2005, **66**, 402.
4. R. W. G. Wyckoff, "Crystal Structures", 2nd ed., Vol. 2, Interscience Publishers, 1964.
5. T. Ressler, *J. Phys. IV*, 1997, **7**, C2.
6. S. I. Zabinsky, J. J. Rehr, A. Ankudinov, R. C. Albers and M. J. Eller, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1995, **52**, 2995.
7. J. A. Solera, J. Garcia and M. G. Proietti, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1994, **51**, 50.
8. V. Dracopoulos, B. Gilbert, B. Børresen, G. M. Photiadis and G. N. Papatheodorou, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1997, **93**, 3081.
9. H. Matsuura, S. Watanabe, T. Sakamoto, T. Kanuma, K. Naoi, M. Hatcho, N. Kitamura, H. Akatsuka, A. K. Adya, T. Honma, T. Uruga and N. Umesaki, *J. Alloys. Compd.*, 2005, in the press.
10. Y. Iwadate, T. Iida, K. Fukushima, J. Mochinaga and M. Gaune-Escard, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1994, **49a**, 811.
11. Y. Okamoto, H. Shiwaku, T. Yaita, H. Narita and H. Tanida, *J. Mol. Struc.*, 2002, **64**, 71.
12. S. Watanabe, A. K. Adya, Y. Okamoto, N. Umesaki, T. Honma, H. Deguchi, M. Horiuchi, T. Yamamoto, S. Noguchi, K. Takase, A. Kajinami, T. Sakamoto, M. Hatcho, N. Kitamura, H. Akatsuka and H. Matsuura, *J. Alloys. Compd.*, 2005, in the press.
13. R. D. Shannon, *Acta Cryst. (A)*, 1976, **32**, 751.

